

FUND MARKET DEVELOPMENT POSSIBILITIES AND SIGNIFICANCE

Nishanova Nargiza Burkhonidinovna

Abdurahmanova Zulayho Olimjanovna

Creative school named after Isokhon Ibrat in the

system of the Agency of Specialized Educational Institutions under the Ministry of

Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

nishanovanargiza8@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14875543>

Abstract: World experience shows that the most important indicators associated with the level of economic development of countries and high per capita national income, including (a large number of types of securities traded on the stock market and high liquidity, high dividend policy in joint-stock companies (JSCs), and improved stock exchange trading systems), are explained by the high level of development of the stock market, in particular, the high share of capitalization of the stock market (SMP) in relation to the volume of gross domestic product (GDP).

Keywords: digital economy, innovations, technologies, e-government, economic growth, stock market, dividend policy, stock trading systems.

Introduction:

The stock market is an important component of the economy, playing a major role in attracting investments and allocating financial resources. Through it, the capital market develops and financial stability is ensured in the country's economy. This article discusses the opportunities for developing the stock market and its impact on the economy. The importance of developing the stock market. Through the development of the stock market: The opportunities for corporations to raise capital increase; The opportunities for investors to earn income expand; Financial stability is ensured in the economy; Contribution to the creation of new jobs; Increase in state budget revenues; Strengthen the stability of the national currency; A significant impetus to economic growth is given. Development opportunities Improvement of legislation and regulation Modernization of laws regulating the stock market; Strengthening mechanisms for protecting the rights of investors; Simplify the licensing process for the stock market; Strengthen the state control and guarantee system. Use of digital technologies Development of electronic trading platforms; Use of blockchain and smart contracts; Expansion of mobile applications and online ¹platforms for investors; Creation of a digitalized stock market infrastructure. Raising the level of education and awareness for investors Organization of financial literacy programs for the population and entrepreneurs; Providing information about the stock market in an accessible and transparent manner; Introduction of financial literacy courses in educational institutions; Conducting online courses and trainings for investors. Attracting foreign investment Creating a favorable environment for international investors; Integration of the national market with international stock markets; Development of tax incentives and other incentive measures; Strengthening mechanisms for cooperation between the public and private sectors. Developing corporate governance Increasing corporate

¹ Mirziyoyev SH.M. 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi PF-60 sonli «2022 - 2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risidagi farmoni

Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Fond bozorini rivojlantirish masalalariga bag'ishlangan yig'ilish bayonoti. 2019 yil 7 oktyabr. <http://xs.uz/uzkr/post/fond-bozorini-rivozhlantirish-masalalari-muhokama-gilindi>.

transparency for companies; Improving reporting standards in joint-stock companies; Strengthening the external audit system; Introducing high-standard management practices for market participants. Introducing new financial instruments Developing diversified investment products; Developing new financial mechanisms for issuers; Increasing access to innovative assets for investors. The development of the stock market ensures sustainable economic growth. This market can be further developed by improving legislation, using digital technologies, improving the investment climate, and developing corporate governance. Therefore, it is important to implement comprehensive measures in this direction. The market can also be further expanded by attracting foreign investment and introducing new financial instruments. Introduction of digital technologies. Development of electronic trading platforms. Use of innovative technologies such as blockchain and smart contracts. Introduction of mobile applications and online services. Increasing financial literacy Organization of financial education programs for the population and business entities. Providing open information about the stock market to the general public. Introduction of courses on the stock market in universities. Attracting foreign investments Integrating the national stock market with international financial markets.

Creating a favorable environment for investors through tax incentives and other incentive measures. Cooperation with international rating agencies. Development of new financial instruments Offering diversified products (ETFs, bonds, IPOs) for investors. Development and introduction of relevant financial mechanisms. Consideration of opportunities for local companies to issue shares on international markets.

A comprehensive approach is required to develop the stock market. The stock market can be further developed by improving legislation, using digital technologies, creating a favorable environment for investors and increasing financial literacy. It not only helps the economy to grow, but also contributes to the welfare of the people.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Акциядорлик жамиятлари ва акциядорларнинг ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилиш тўғрисида”ги Қонуни (янги таҳрирда). 2014 йил 6 май.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Бухгалтерия ҳисоби тўғрисида” ги Қонуни (янги таҳрирда). 2016 йил 13 апрел.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Аудиторлик фаолияти тўғрисида” ги Қонуни (янги таҳрирда). 2000 йил 26 май.
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида” ги ПФ-4947-сонли Фармони. 2017 йил 7 феврал.
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Солиқ маъмуриятчилигини тубдан такомиллаштириш, солиқлар ва бошқа мажбурий тўловларнинг йиғилувчанлигини ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ги Фармони. 2017 йил 18 июл.
6. Мирзиёев Ш. Танқидий таҳлил, қатъий тартиб-интизом ва шахсий жавобгарлик – ҳар бир раҳбар фаолиятининг кундалик қонидаси бўлиши керак. – Т.: “Ўзбекистон”, 2017. – 104 б.
7. Артеменко Д.А. Проблемы институционализации независимой медиасии

взаимодействия бизнеса и государства в процедурах налогового администрирования. // Вопросы регулирования экономики. – Москва, 2010. – №4. – С. 7.

8. Маҳмудов Н.М., Адизов С.Р. Солиқларнинг макроиқтисодий кўрсаткичларга таъсири баҳолаш: назария, амалиёт ва моделлаштириш. Монография. – Т.: “Фан”, 2014. –160 б.

9. Машарибов Ж. Солиқ маслаҳати: ривожланиш истиқболлари. // Солиқлар ва божхона хабарлари. – Тошкент, 2009. – №1. – Б. 3-4.

10. Ташмурадова Б., КурбоновЖ. Корпоратив тузилмалар ва давлат ўртасидаги ўзаро молиявий муносабатлар тизими. // Бизнес-эксперт. – Тошкент, 2015. – №11. – Б. 10. (7-11)

11. Адиллов М.Қ. Тадбиркорлик фаолиятида солиқларни режалаштириш. – Т.: “Норма”, 2012. – 420 б.

12. Ваҳобов А.В., Жумаев Н.Х., Бурхонов У.А. Халқаро молия муносабатлари. Дарслик. – Т.: “Шарқ”, 2003. – 400 б.

13. <http://www.gov.uz> (Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳукумати портали).

14. <http://www.ziyonet.uz> (Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги сайти).

15. <http://www.lex.uz> (Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси).

16. <http://www.stat.uz> (Ўзбекистон Республикаси Давлат Статистика қўмитаси).

17. <http://www.uza.uz>.

18. <http://www.cisstat.com> (Межгосударственный статистический комитет СНГ).

19. <http://www.oecd.org>.

20. <http://www.ebiblioteka.ru> (РФ электрон кутубхонаси сайти).

21. <http://www.mckinsey.com>.

22. <http://www.industrytap.com>